

NEURAL NETWORK LEARNING TECHNIQUES COMPARISON FOR A MULTIPHYSICS SECOND ORDER LOW-PASS FILTER

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Abstract— The design process of high frequency (HF) structures has been a major challenge in recent years, with the increasing demand for better performance and more complex designs. This process is even worse when considering multiphysics simulation, such as thermal and mechanical physics combined with the electromagnetic response of the circuit. The traditional approach of trial and error can be highly time consuming and prone to error while the use of direct optimization techniques can also be computationally expensive. To speed up the design process, artificial neural networks (ANN) have been extensively used to develop fast and accurate surrogate models of high-frequency structures. In this work, we compare the performance of three ANN learning techniques (Levenberg-Marquardt, Bayesian, and Resilient) for modeling a multi-physics second order low-pass filter implemented in COMSOL. Results demonstrate that the Bayesian ANN exhibits the best performance for efficiently and accurately model the multi-physical response of HF structures.

Keywords— Artificial neural networks, multi-physical, low-pass filter, Bayesian, Levenberg-Marquardt BP, Resilient BP

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial neural networks (ANNs) have been extensively used to develop fast and accurate surrogate models of high-frequency structures characterized by computationally expensive electromagnetic (EM) simulations [1, 2]. EM efficient trained artificial neural network (EM-ANN) allows the EM circuit design simulation and optimization to be fast and accurate [3-5].

One of the key advantages of combining multiphysics simulations and ANNs is the ability of these last to handle non-linear optimization problems [6]. Different learning techniques can be applied to develop ANN, such as the Levenberg-Marquardt ANN, Resilient ANN and Bayesian ANN.

The Levenberg-Marquardt method is a trust region algorithm which aims to find a minimum of a function over a space of parameters. The trust region of the objective is modeled by a quadratic function and when the adequate fit is found the region is expanded [6, 7].

The resilient backpropagation (BP) method is based on gradients. Like Manhattan update rule, resilient BP algorithm uses only the sign of the gradient to determine a weight delta.

Also, it maintains separate weight deltas for each weight and bias and adapts them during training [8].

The Bayesian ANN uses statistical distributions to quantify uncertainty introduced by models in terms of outputs and weights. Compared to a standard ANN, Bayesian ANN focuses on marginalization instead of optimization, the estimate of parameters is done by the maximum a posteriori instead of maximum likelihood estimators. The optimal value is found by using Markov Chain Monte Carlo, Variational Interference or Normalizing Flows instead of gradient descent [9].

In this work, a comparison of the three learning methods is done to determine the best ANN surrogate model for a second order multi-physics low pass filter implemented in COMSOL. The multi-physics simulation considers the electromagnetic, thermal and mechanical response of the structure under study.

This work is organized as follows: Section I gives a brief introduction to the purpose of this work. Section II describes the multi-physical circuit under study. Section III describes the process for developing ANN surrogate models. Section IV shows the corresponding results and finally some important remarks are given in the Conclusions section.

II. MULTI-PHYSICAL CIRCUIT

The microstrip filter used in this work is modeled in COMSOL and consist of a low pass microstrip filter exhibiting a multi-physical behavior (EM, thermal, and mechanical). Multi-physics simulations are very high time consuming and computationally expensive. The corresponding model for the low pass filter is shown in Fig 1.

The filter structure is implemented in COMSOL using a dielectric substrate with a height $H = 0.794$ mm, a relative dielectric constant $\epsilon_r = 2.2$ and a dielectric loss tangent $\tan(\delta) = 0.0025$. The feed-line width is defined as $W_p = 2.191$ mm to achieve 50- Ω input/output lines. The selected feed-line length for the filter is $L_p = 5.079$ mm, $W_1 = 2.467$ mm, $S_1 = 5.053$ mm, and $L_1 = 5.062$ mm. All metallic traces are defined as copper with a thickness $t = 0.17$ μm [11].

To be properly simulated, a simulation bounding box is required, with $x_{\text{gap}} = 10.95$ mm defined as the lateral separation from the box edge and $H_{\text{air}} = 7.94$ mm defined as the air layer

height. Horizontal lumped ports were used with a port length $L_{\text{port}} = 0.21$ mm. For the structure meshing we follow the scheme proposed in [12].

Each multi-physics simulation takes approximately 20 minutes using a personal computer with a core i7 processor and 16GB RAM.

Fig. 1. Geometry of the low-pass microstrip filter implemented in COMSOL. Figure taken from [11].

III. ANN SURROGATE MODEL

The development of a neural network model includes the generation of representative training data within the region of interest (called learning base points) and the selection of the network topology and training techniques. Once trained, the ANN model performance is measured by using random testing base points within the region of interest.

The multilayer perceptron (MLP) neural network is appropriate for this functional mapping problem [13]. We used a 3-layer perceptron (3LP) to implement our neuro-model, with n inputs, h hidden neurons, and m outputs. The required complexity of the ANN, determined by h , depends on the generalization performance for a given set of testing data [14].

To obtain the best ANN surrogate model, three different learning algorithms were implemented: Levenberg-Marquardt BP, resilient BP, and Bayesian Regularization.

To train and generate the ANN surrogate models, we used the Neural Network toolbox included in Matlab. The training algorithms were set in Matlab by using `trainFcn = 'trainlm'` for Levenberg-Marquardt BP, `trainFcn = 'trainrp'` for resilient BP and, `trainFcn = 'trainbr'` for Bayesian regularization.

For developing the ANN models, 80% of the total amount of learning base points were used for training purposes, 10% for validation, and 10% for testing.

For measuring the ANN performance, we calculate the mean learning square error (MSE), the maximum learning error (MLE) and the maximum testing error (MTE). The MSE is calculated by obtaining the mean of the differences power by 2 between the ANN and the circuit response at the training points. The MLE is calculated by obtaining the maximum difference between the ANN and the circuit response at the training points. The MTE measures the maximum difference between the ANN and the circuit response at the simulated random testing points.

The final number of hidden neurons for each training algorithm, using the procedure in [15], is defined as the point

where the testing error does not improve with respect to the training error.

IV. ANN MODELING RESULTS

For developing the ANN surrogate models we generate 50 learning base points uniformly distributed from -50 °C to 100 °C. We also use as inputs 51 uniformly distributed frequency points, from 0.1 GHz to 4 GHz. The circuit response $|S_{21}|$ is used as the target for the ANN model. To measure the generalization performance, we generate 10 random temperature testing points within the temperature range. For each training algorithm we developed 20 ANN models and select the model with the best generalization performance.

Corresponding MSE, MLE, and MTE for the three learning techniques can be seen in Fig. 2. The number of hidden neurons selected for the best ANN models, following the procedure in [15], can be seen in Fig. 3. For the Bayesian regularization ANN $h = 1$, for the Levenberg-Marquardt BP ANN $h = 4$, and for the Resilient BP ANN $h = 1$.

According to the obtained results, the best generalization performance error is achieved by the Bayesian regularization technique. Corresponding results at some testing base points can be seen in Fig. 4. It is observed a very good match between the Bayesian ANN and the COMSOL model responses.

Fig. 2. Corresponding MSE, MLE, and MTE for the Bayesian, Resilient, and Levenberg-Marquardt ANN using 20 trials.

Fig. 3. Learning and testing errors and corresponding number of h hidden neurons for each ANN training algorithm.

Fig. 4. COMSOL (o) and Bayesian ANN (x) model responses at some testing random points.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a comparison between three ANN learning techniques (Bayesian regularization, Resilient BP, and Levenberg – Marquardt BP) was done. The purpose was to model the response $|S_{21}|$ of a multi-physical second order low-pass filter implemented in COMSOL subject to temperature variations. For training the ANN models, 50 learning base points within a region of interest were simulated and to measure the generalization performance, 10 random testing base points were generated. For each learning technique, 20 ANN models were developed. The best ANN model was selected according to the model with the minimum MSE, MLE, and MTE. Corresponding results show that the Bayesian ANN exhibits the best performance, having a very good match between the COMSOL

and the Bayesian ANN model responses at testing points. These results show that Bayesian ANN model is suitable to represent the multi-physical response of high frequency structures.

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